

Analysing Non-Tariff Measures (Ntms) for Trade Policy: In Case of Uzbekistan

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Abstract: In this article, I outline the fundamental challenges that countries, with a focus on Uzbekistan, encounter when addressing non-tariff measures (NTMs) and explore how optimizing these barriers can enhance international trade. Given that international trade significantly influences economic growth, it's imperative for governments to grasp the intricacies of trade policy, implementing the effective use of tariffs and non-tariff measures. Additionally, it assessed the regulatory frameworks, administrative procedures, and institutional structures in Uzbekistan that are linked to the implementation of non-tariff measures (NTMs). The research's findings aim to shed light on the potential benefits and drawbacks associated with the adoption and enforcement of key NTMs in trade policy, as well as the challenges and opportunities tied to their execution and enforcement.

Definition and importance of NTMs:

Non-tariff barriers encompass any measures, apart from customs duties, that regulate and affect the entry or exit of goods into or from a nation. According to the paper written by RW. Staiger (Non-tariff Measures and the WTO, 2012) NTMs can be categorized into three distinct groups. The first category comprises NTMs applied to imports, including measures like import quotas, import bans, import licensing requirements, and fees related to customs procedures and administration. The second category includes NTMs affecting exports, such as export duties, export subsidies, export quotas, export bans, and voluntary export constraints. These initial two categories involve NTMs that are enforced at the border, either for incoming or outgoing goods. The third and final category involves NTMs implemented within the domestic economy, often referred to as "behind-the-border" measures. Various types of non-tariff measures on trade volume between Uzbekistan and its major trade partners are examined. The following graphs illustrate the trend of international trade and imports from 2000 to 2021.

Figure 8: Foreign trade turnover of goods and services (in \$bn)

Note: Foreign trade turnover as the sum of imports and exports of the country.

Figure 9: Import trend in Uzbekistan

Source: <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika>

Gravity model

The gravity model is a theoretical framework employed within the field of economics to anticipate and elucidate trade patterns between countries. The model is characterized by an equation, commonly referred to as the gravity model of world trade (equation 1-1), which draws an analogy to Newton's law of gravity. This comparison arises from the resemblance in nature between the gravitational attraction observed between two objects—proportional to the product of their masses and inversely related to the distance separating them—and the trade interactions between two nations. In a similar vein, when other factors remain constant, the trade volume between any two countries is anticipated to be directly proportional to the multiplication of their respective Gross Domestic Products (GDPs), while inversely diminishing with the increase in distance between them. By utilizing this model, researchers aim to uncover and comprehend the underlying mechanisms driving trade dynamics across various nations.

$$T_{ij} = A \times Y_i \times Y_j / D_{ij} \text{ (1-1)}$$

where A is a constant term;

T_{ij} is the value of trade between country i and j ;

Y_i is country i 's GDP;

Y_j is country j 's GDP;

D_{ij} is the distance between the two countries.

Gravity Equation of the research

In this research, a significant contribution is made by incorporating additional variables into the basic gravity model. Specifically, the study introduces the NTBs index (non-tariff barriers index) from the years 2003 to 2022. By incorporating these explanatory variables alongside the existing variables in the gravity model, a comprehensive regression equation can be formulated to capture the dynamics of trade.

$$\ln(\text{imp}_{ijt}) = \alpha + \beta_1(\text{NTB}_{it}) + \beta_2 \ln(1 + \text{tar}_{it}) + \beta_3 \ln(\text{GDP}_i * \text{GDP}_j) + \beta_4(\text{DIS}_{ij}) + \beta_5(\text{RTA}_{ijt}) + \text{dummy}(\text{YEAR}) + \text{dummy}(\text{PARTNER}) + \varepsilon_{ijt}$$

(2-1)

$$\ln(\text{exp}_{ijt}) = \alpha + \beta_1(\text{NTB}_{jt}) + \beta_2 \ln(1 + \text{tar}_{jt}) + \beta_3 \ln(\text{GDP}_i * \text{GDP}_j) + \beta_4(\text{DIS}_{ij}) + \beta_5(\text{RTA}_{ijt}) + \text{dummy}(\text{YEAR}) + \text{dummy}(\text{PARTNER}) + \varepsilon_{ijt}$$

(2-2)

$\ln(\text{imp})_{ijt}$: import volume from country j to i (*Uzbekistan*) in year t ;

$\ln(\text{exp})_{ijt}$: export volume from country i (*Uzbekistan*) to country j in year t ;

NTB_{it} : Non-tariff barriers protection level index of country i (*Uzbekistan*) in year t ;

NTB_{jt} : Non-tariff barriers protection level index of country j (*trading country*) in year t ;

tar_{it} : MFN simple average tariff rate of Uzbekistan in year t ;

tar_{jt} : MFN simple average tariff rate of B country in year t ;

$\text{GDP}_i * \text{GDP}_j$: The product of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of two countries, i and j , in year t ;

DIS_{ij} : distance between countries i and j ;

$\text{dummy}(\text{YEAR})$: YEAR dummy variable is also included to control the specificity of particular economic circumstances in each year;

$\text{dummy}(\text{PARTNER})$: PARTNER dummy variable is also included control the specificity of particular economic circumstances in each country;

RTA_{ijt} : RTA dummy variable between country i and j in time t ;

ε_{ijt} : Idiosyncratic error term.

In the first regression equation (2-1), the dependent variable is defined as the import volume of Uzbekistan. This analysis aims at ascertaining the relationship between trade barriers and the import volume of Uzbekistan, particularly when Uzbekistan implements non-tariff measures against its major trading partners. The model takes into account the GDP of both countries, the distance between them as influential factors as well as contiguity factor. In addition to the non-tariff measures, this study will also examine the impact of various other factors on bilateral trade by incorporating dummy variables. Furthermore, tariff barriers, despite being reduced through the conclusion of recent Free Trade Agreements (FTAs), will be considered as another significant explanatory variable. Regarding the subsequent regression equation (2-2), the dependent variable is characterized as the export volume of Uzbekistan to its major trading partners. This equation aims to investigate the influence of trade policies adopted by partner nations, particularly the implementation of Non-Tariff Barriers (NTBs), on the dynamics of Uzbekistan's exports. The remaining variables remain consistent with those utilized in the preceding Equation 2-1. To enhance the precision of the analysis, YEAR and

PARTNER dummy variables are also included. These variables allow for controlling the specific economic circumstances in each year and accounting for the distinct effects of each of the PARTNER countries.

General Information on Variables

In this research study, key explanatory variable called the non-tariff barriers index is included. This index is derived from the economic freedom data provided by the Fraser Institute. The dataset encompasses information on non-tariff barriers and tariff rates¹ spanning the period from 2003 to 2022. Further details pertaining to the variables are showcased in [Table 4] which provides descriptive statistics for the set of variables.

[Table 4] Descriptive statistics of variables

Variables	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max	Median
ln(imp)	5.44	1.57	1.03	8.75	5.44
ln(exp)	4.3	2.11	0.001	7.87	5.21
NTB of Uzb	6.76	0.75	5.56	8.1	6.8
NTB of B	5.66	0.97	3.5	8.64	5.64
Tariff of Uzb	13.57	3.05	6.47	17.42	14.97
Tariff of B	8.19	1.18	3.8	10.2	8.57
Distance	4202.87	3470	480.29	13836.3	3128.88
ln(GDP)	24.08	2.29	16.78	28.35	24.3

Regression Analysis

[Table 5] Summary of Variables

Variables	Explanation	Source
IMPORT	Uzbekistan's import volume ²	UN Comtrade ³ and UZSTAT ⁴
EXPORT	Uzbekistan's export volume	UN Comtrade and UZSTAT
NTB UZB	Non-Tariff Barriers Index of Uzbekistan	Fraser Institute ⁵ and MIIT ⁶
NTB FOR	Non-Tariff Barriers Index of trading countries	Fraser Institute
TAR UZB	MFN simple average of Uzbekistan	MIIT and World Bank
TAR FOR	MFN simple average of trading countries	WTO ⁷ and World Bank ⁸
GDP	GDP in US million dollars, taken logarithm	World Bank
DIS	Distance between two countries	Cepii ⁹
RTA	RTA to capture trade agreement	WTO I-TIP ¹⁰
CONT	Contiguity	Cepii
YEAR	YEAR dummy variable	
PARTNER	PARTNER dummy variabl	

¹ **MFN simple average:** The "MFN simple average" is a concept related to tariffs, specifically the average tariff rates applied by a country to its imports from all its trading partners under the MFN principle. It is a way to measure the overall level of trade barriers (tariffs) a country imposes on its imports. Mathematically, the formula for calculating the MFN simple average tariff rate can be expressed as: $MFN \text{ Simple Average} = \frac{\sum_i^n \text{Tariff rate}_i}{n}$, where n= total number of tariff rates; Tariff rate_i = tariff rate for the product *i*th product.

² Imports' volume, expressed in US million dollars, then transformed logarithmically.

³ UNcomtrade: <https://comtrade.un.org/data/>

⁴ UZSTAT: <https://stat.uz>

⁵ Economic Freedom: <https://www.fraserinstitute.org/studies/economic-freedom>

⁶ MIIT: <https://miit.uz/en>

⁷ <http://tariffdata.wto.org/>

⁸ <https://wits.worldbank.org/tariff/trains/country-byhs6product.aspx?lang=en>

⁹ Cepii: <http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/publications/wp/abstract.asp?NoDoc=3877>

¹⁰ I-TIP: <http://rtais.wto.org/UI/PublicMaintainRTAHome.aspx>

Hypothesis models

The increasing number of Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs) has significantly reduced tariff barriers. However, despite this, international trade remains influenced by border-related factors in light of recent protectionist trends. Assuming that the decline in global trade can be attributed to the rise of non-tariff measures, a series of regression analyses involving six models were undertaken for each gravity equation (2-1) and (2-2). Each model is evaluated using various panel data approaches, including the Pooling regression model, Fixed Effect model (FE), and Random Effect model (RE). By comparing the outcomes of these different approaches, we can determine which model provides the most accurate representation of the relationship under investigation. This comparison enables us to identify the model that best captures the underlying patterns and dynamics within the data, leading to more reliable and insightful results.

For import case:

Model 1-1: H0: Increasing non-tariff barriers (NTBs) in Uzbekistan do not lead to a reduction in imports, indicating that the country's rising NTBs are not significantly connected to import levels.

H1: Increased NTB result in a reduction of imports.

Model 1-2: H0: Higher NTB and higher tariff rates of Uzbekistan do not result in a decrease in import, which suggests that the growing tariff rates and more NTB of the country have no significant relevance to imports.

H1: Higher tariff rates of Uzbekistan and higher NTB lead to a decrease in import.

Model 1-3: H0: In the case of countries that have entered into Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs) with Uzbekistan, implying reduced tariff barriers, an increase in non-tariff barriers (NTBs) does not lead to a decline in imports.

H1: For countries that have signed in RTA with Uzbekistan, which means there exists lower tariff barriers for these countries, higher NTB leads to a decrease in imports.

Model 1-4: H0: Considering YEAR and PARTNER dummy, higher NTB does not result in a decrease in imports, when the partner country signed in RTA with Uzbekistan.

H1: Considering YEAR and PARTNER dummy, higher NTB leads to reduction of imports when the partner country signed in RTA with Uzbekistan.

For export case:

Model 2-1: H0: Increasing non-tariff barriers (NTBs) do not lead to a reduction in exports, indicating that rising NTBs are not significantly connected to import levels.

H1: Increased non-tariff barriers (NTBs) are associated with a decline in exports, indicating a negative correlation between NTBs and export levels.

Model 2-2: H0: Higher tariff rates and higher NTB do not result in a decrease in export, which suggests that the growing tariffs and more NTB of partner countries have no significant relevance to Uzbekistan's exports.

H1: Higher tariffs and more NTB of partner countries leads to a decrease in exports.

Model 2-3: H0: In the case of countries that have entered into Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs) with Uzbekistan, where lower tariff barriers are established for Uzbekistan's goods, an increase in non-tariff barriers (NTBs) does not lead to a decrease in exports.

H1: For countries that have entered into Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs) with Uzbekistan, resulting in lower tariff barriers for Uzbekistan's goods, an increase in non-tariff barriers (NTBs) leads to a decrease in imports.

Model 2-4: H0: Considering YEAR and PARTNER dummy, higher NTB does not result in a decrease in exports, when the partner country signed in RTA with Uzbekistan.

H1: Considering YEAR and PARTNER dummy, higher NTB leads to reduction of exports when the partner country signed in RTA with Uzbekistan.

Results and analysis

Initially, the empirical investigation involves utilizing the combined Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of both Uzbekistan and the partner country, along with the geographical distance between them—which are fundamental variables of the gravity model. Following the gravity model's equation, it is anticipated that GDP will exhibit a positive influence, whereas distance will exert a negative impact. According to [Table 7] and [Table 8] below, Increasing GDP is associated with higher trade volumes, whereas both export and import shows an inverse relationship with distance, which exactly coincides the gravity model theory.

[Table 7] Regression outcome: basic gravity model for import

DEPENDENT VARIABLE: IMPORT	
INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	Coefficient (std. error)
GDP	0.471*** (0.0334)
DISTANCE(10 ³)	-0.3065*** (2.21e-05)
CONSTANT	-4.604*** (0.766)
Observations	300
R-squared	0.469
F-statistics	198.70
Prob(F-statistics)	0.0000

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

[Table 8] Regression outcome: basic gravity model for export

DEPENDENT VARIABLE: EXPORT	
INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	Coefficient (std. error)
GDP	0.315*** (0.045)
DISTANCE(10 ³)	-0.4032*** (2.99e-05)
CONSTANT	-1.531*** (1.037)
Observations	300
R-squared	0.38
F-statistics	90.99
Prob(F-statistics)	0.0000

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Initially, following an analysis of the fundamental gravity model, we conducted regression analyses using solely the NTB independent variable for both import and export scenarios. The outcomes, as presented in [Table 9], unequivocally demonstrate that NTBs imposed by

Uzbekistan have a notable impact on import volume, contributing to a significant decrease of 0.93%. Similarly, when focusing on exports, it is evident that NTBs imposed by Uzbekistan's trading partners exert a significant effect on export volume, resulting in a noteworthy reduction of 0.45%. This underscores how a small changes in NTBs can yield substantial consequences.

The results derived from an in-depth analysis using panel data and a variety of regression models shed light on the intricate dynamics of non-tariff measures (NTMs) imposed by Uzbekistan, NTB index of partner countries and their influence on import and export volume in relation to trading partners. Across the spectrum of examined models including Pooling regression, Fixed effect, and Random effect, distinct patterns emerged. According to the [Table 8] and [Table 10] underneath, firstly, irrespective of the specific model employed, a consistent observation emerged: the presence of NTMs was consistently associated with a statistically significant decline in import volume at 1% significance level which is coincide with the central assumption of this paper, which holds that different non-tariff barriers negatively affect trade volume, 1 unit upsurge of Uzbekistan’s NTB index corresponds to an approximate 0.5% reduction in the import volume of Uzbekistan ($p < 0.001$), consistently observed across different model specifications. Regarding export, in the case of the Pooling regression model, the presence of NTMs is consistently linked to a statistically significant decline in export volume at a 1% significance level. However, when considering the Fixed effect and Random effect models, the correlation between NTMs and export volume becomes more nuanced. Models 1-2 and 2-2 represent the regression analysis focusing on the influence of tariff rates on Uzbekistan bilateral trade, with the addition of the variable “MFNUZ” and “MFNB”, simple average tariff rate of Uzbekistan and trading countries respectively. As expected, MFN exhibits a negative correlation with overall imports and exports from all trading countries. Nevertheless, even with the inclusion of the MFN variable, NTB continues to exert a negative effect on imports from partner countries. This assertion is supported by the negative coefficient of NTB presented in the second section of [Table 10]. As can be seen from the table tariff effect is not statistically significant in Pooling regression model, which urges us to exercise caution in definitively inferring the existence or strength of this relationship. Consequently, in alignment with the hypothesis, it can be deduced that the impact of non-tariff barriers remains pertinent, even after accounting for tariff rates.

Importantly, the R-squared value of 0.513 in Pooled and more than 0.71 for other two models collectively indicated that around 70% of import volume and 50% in Pooled of export volume variability was elucidated by the integrated variables, irrespective of the model's specifications. Significantly, the F-statistic, reaching statistical significance ($p < 0.001$), underscored the reliability of the model across the various specifications.

**[Table 9] Regression outcome:
Including only NTB variable**

DEPENDENT VARIABLE: IMPORT	
INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	Coefficient (std. error)
NTB	-0.927*** (0.109)
CONSTANT	11.705 (0.740)
Observations	300
R-squared	0.195

DEPENDENT VARIABLE: EXPORT	
INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	Coefficient (std. error)
NTB	-0.445*** (0.115)
CONSTANT	6.867*** (0.663)
Observations	300
R-squared	0.047

[Table 10] Regression outcome: Model 1-1 and 1-2**DEPENDENT VARIABLE: IMPORT**

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	MODEL 1-1			MODEL 1-2		
	Pooled	FE	RE	Pooled	FE	RE
NTB	-0.488*** (0.094)	-0.454*** (0.081)	-0.446*** (0.080)	-0.342*** (0.144)	-0.454*** (0.081)	-0.446*** (0.080)
GDP	0.393*** (0.035)	0.309*** (0.044)	0.316*** (0.043)	0.396*** (0.035)	0.309*** (0.044)	0.316*** (0.043)
DISTANCE	-0.0003*** (0.00002)	-	-0.0003*** (0.0001)	-0.0003*** (0.00002)	-	-0.0003*** (0.0001)
TARIFF (MFN)	-	-	-	-0.045 (0.034)	-0.040*** (0.014)	-0.040*** (0.014)
CONSTANT	0.450 (1.217)		2.476* (1.417)	0.10 (1.259)		2.476* (1.417)
Observations	300	300	300	300	300	300
R-squared	0.513	0.719	0.713	0.516	0.719	0.713
F-statistics	104.027***	241.075	733.813***	78.664***	241.075	733.813***

* p<0.1, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

Δr+i

Regression results, namely [Model 1-3], were conducted to examine the impact of Regional Trade Agreements (RTA) on Uzbekistan's imports, incorporating the variable RTA. To avoid heteroskedasticity issue, robust standard error was used for estimation. As anticipated, RTA exhibits a positive correlation with total imports from all nations, specifically, one unit increase in RTA leads 1.4% growth in import. It is noteworthy that the variable for tariff rates (MFN) variable was deliberately excluded in this analysis due to the evident robust relationship between tariff rates and RTAs. However, for countries that have engaged in RTAs, the presence of NTB continues to adversely influence imports of Uzbekistan. This observation is underscored by the negative coefficient of NTB in the first three columns of [Table 10]. Consequently, aligned with the hypothesis, it can be inferred that the influence of non-tariff barriers remains valid even after accounting for the presence of RTA.

Subsequently, the regression outcome's third column is based on the consideration of YEAR and PARTNER dummy variables to gauge the time effect. Notably, these variables have been omitted from the provided table. An intriguing observation arises as YEAR dummies display a lack of statistical significance, except for the year 2010, 2011 and 2016 which coincides with the end of the global financial crisis and new era of Uzbekistan. Moreover, as the years progress beyond 2018, the coefficients associated with the YEAR variables exhibit a negative trend. This trend suggests that non-tariff barriers have intensified over time, particularly in the aftermath of the financial crisis, when developed economies like the US and China grappled with domestic economic recessions. As anticipated, NTB maintains a negative correlation with import volume. Remarkably, RTA continues to yield a positive coefficient in the Random Effect model, signifying its constructive influence on international trade. However, the table underscores that even in the presence of bilateral RTAs, the impact of non-tariff barriers remains valid in flow of international trade. A scatterplot was inserted in [Appendix A] to visualize the relationship between the import and the variable NTB while differentiating by country. In considering the remaining variables, GDP and DISTANCE showcase a positive and negative correlation with exports, respectively, aligning with the foundational principles of the gravity model. Time-fixed effects testing was employed to capture unobserved time-specific characteristics. The p-value of 0.35 is indicating that null hypothesis (that the individual effects are not significant) cannot be rejected and conclude that including the individual effects (fixed effects) in the model does not improve the model's fit.

The Hausman test is a statistical test used to decide whether a fixed effects model or a random

effects model is more appropriate for a panel data analysis. The Hausman test helps to choose between these two approaches based on the characteristics of your data. If the p-value is smaller than 0.05 then time-fixed effects are used. In this example [Table 13], p-value = 0.5572 suggests that we do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. In the context of the Hausman test, the null hypothesis typically states that the random effects assumptions hold, which means that the unobserved individual-specific effects are not systematically correlated with the independent variables.

[Table 12] Regression outcome: [Model 1-3 and 1-4]

DEPENDENT VARIABLE: IMPORT

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES	MODEL 1-3			MODEL 1-4	
	Pooled	FE	RE	FE	RE
NTB	-0.186 (0.129)	-0.454*** (0.111)	-0.433*** (0.112)	-0.263* (0.153)	-0.248* (0.133)
TARIFF (MFN)	-0.052 (0.030)	-0.040*** (0.0112)	-0.041*** (0.0114)	-	-
RTA	1.399*** (0.152)	-	1.066* (0.543)	-	1.407 (2.902)
YEAR	-	-	-	INCLUDED	INCLUDED
PARTNER	-	-	-	INCLUDED	INCLUDED
GDP	0.5166*** (0.034)	0.309*** (0.067)	0.326*** (0.067)	0.510*** (0.105)	0.521*** (0.0885)
DISTANCE	-0.0003*** (0.00002)	-	-0.0002*** (0.00005)	omitted	-0.00025** (0.0001)
CONSTANT	-4.3856*** (1.2102)	-	1.641 (1.471)	-	-4.263 (3.26)
Observations	300	300	300	300	300
R-squared	0.624	0.719	0.714	0.738	0.734
F-statistics/Chisq	97.663***	49.23	181.744	37.317***	765.117***

* p<0.1, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

[Table 13] Housman test result

Coefficients	Import	Export
chisq	2.074	11.468
p-value	0.5572	0.01

Implication

Across the outcomes of eight regression models, a consistent pattern emerges, highlighting the negative association between border effects, notably non-tariff barriers (the central focus of this study), and both exports and imports. Initially, the basic parameters of the gravity model's regression analysis reveal that greater GDP and shorter distances enhance trade volume between nations. Furthermore, an examination of a country's comprehensive index of non-tariff barriers (NTBs) suggests a direct correlation: higher index values correspond to more pronounced negative trade impacts. Interestingly, even after accounting for the impact of tariff barriers through Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs), non-tariff measures (NTMs) maintain their influence, even in countries bound by RTAs. This underscores the necessity of devising strategies to address non-tariff measures as a means to counteract border effects moving forward.

Despite the incorporation of YEAR and PARTNER dummy variables, the persistence of the NTB effect remains a significant finding. This outcome underscores the multifaceted nature of non-

tariff barriers (NTBs) and their enduring influence on bilateral trade relationships. These barriers, ranging from regulatory complexities to procedural bottlenecks, can exert a substantial drag on trade even in the presence of other contextual factors. The implications of these results are far-reaching. They suggest that enhancing trade facilitation measures and streamlining cumbersome administrative procedures could yield remarkable gains in bilateral trade volumes. By pinpointing and addressing specific non-effective barriers, policymakers have an opportunity to unlock substantial trade potential between partner countries. The pathway to achieving such gains necessitates a targeted approach that combines comprehensive policy reforms with the insights gained from these empirical findings.

In essence, this study highlights that while various factors influence international trade dynamics, the persistent influence of NTBs demands focused attention. The pursuit of trade growth calls for a holistic approach that not only considers the macroeconomic and geopolitical landscape but also delves into the intricacies of trade-related regulations and procedures. By doing so, countries can harness the full potential of their trade relationships and forge a path toward more prosperous economic partnerships.

Conclusion

The central focus of this paper revolves around the relationship between non-tariff measures (NTMs) and the volume of trade. Our regression analysis effectively substantiates this connection. It confirms that when Uzbekistan encounters NTMs imposed by its trade partners, this exerts a negative impact on its exports. Likewise, as anticipated, when Uzbekistan implements these barriers for imported goods, it results in a decrease in imports. Furthermore, our findings reveal that sanitary and phytosanitary (SPS) and technical barriers to trade (TBT) measures wield a more substantial influence compared to other forms of NTMs. Unfortunately, due to data opacity, we were unable to access specific information related to SPS and TBT measures in Uzbekistan. Nevertheless, our comprehensive dataset, encompassing the non-tariff barrier index, average tariff rates, and information on regional trade agreements (RTAs), sufficiently substantiates the conclusion that NTMs contribute to a reduction in bilateral trade and, consequently, an inefficient allocation of resources.

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